

Sophytes' Helmet: Origin, Symbolism, and Apotheosis

LLOYD W. H. TAYLOR

This study examines the development of the depiction of the helmet worn by the male head on the coinage of Sophytes and its implications for alternative theories of attribution of the coinage. This was an Attic military helmet of the 3rd century BC. It is presented in a numismatic depiction that evolved from the preceding portrayal of Athena's helmet on the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage struck under Andragoras of Parthia. Calibration of the changes in coin fabric and the details of the helmet depicted on the Series 2 coinage to identical developments in the Athenian coinage of the 3rd century BC serve to date its emission to the middle of the 3rd century BC. Detailed analysis reveals that the obverse iconography of the Sophytes' coinage developed independently of the superficially similar obverse iconography of the victory issues of Seleukos I struck at Susa. Consequently, there is no basis for the frequently inferred chronological nexus between the two coinages. Furthermore, art history considerations suggest that Sophytes, via the ornamentation of his helmet, sought to assimilate his image with that of Ares, in a claim to divinity that can only have emerged in the mid-third century BC when Greek religious and cultural norms had evolved to accept the apotheosis of leaders. An examination of the imagery of the gold stater emission struck by Sophytes predecessor, Andragoras, identifies the precedent for Sophytes claim to divinity in a symbolic numismatic narrative that reflects the rising existential threat to the secessionist march state of Parthia posed by the invading Parni, led by Arsaces.

BACKGROUND

A recently published study of the imitative Athenian coinage formerly attributed to the region of the Oxus Valley (Baktria) established the case for its reattribution to Parthia during the satrapy of Andragoras, who it appears was briefly succeeded by Sophytes prior to the complete conquest of the province by the Parni under the leadership of Arsaces.¹ This placed the coinage in the period c. 250-238 BC. The study noted three important developments in the transition from the earlier (Series 1) to the later (Series 2) imitative Athenian coinage. The 12 o'clock die adjustment and square reverse dies of the former changed to a 6 o'clock die adjustment, accompanied by the use of cylindrical dies on the latter (Figure 1). Initially Series 2 maintained the imitative Athenian iconography of Series 1, but following the adoption of 6 o'clock die axis a new detail was added to Athena's helmet. A circular loop, or volute termination was added to the decorative pediment visor² on the helmet

¹ Taylor (2019): 53-54.

² This decorative element on the helmet is characterised by an inverted V shape on its upper frontal edge coincident with the centre line of the helmet. It is also described as a pediment, reflecting its resemblance to the architectural form of the same name. This design had its origins on Ionian and Corinthian helmets of the 6th century BC as a ridge added to the forehead encircling the front of the helmet above the eyes. It served to deflect downward directed glancing blows to the front of the helmet. By the 4th century BC it had become a prominent decorative device, rather than a purely functional form.

above Athena's ear (Figures 1c-d, and 2b). Once established on Series 2, the volute motif on the helmet was maintained in the later depictions of Athena on the Series 3 (Athena /eagle) and Series 7 (Sophytes Athena/cockerel)³ coinage, as well as that depicted on the Sophytes Series 8 (male head/cockerel) emission (Figure 2). In the transition from Series 7 to Series 8 the depiction of the helmet evolved further, dropping the conventions of the Athenian prototype to become a true-to-life depiction of a 3rd century BC Attic type military helmet. This saw the decorative motifs of the Athenian prototype abandoned, accompanied by the addition of a cheek guard to the profile (Figure 2d-e). Due to space limitations in the original article detailing the coinage, the exposition of the full nature and significance of these developments was curtailed. The following study seeks to address this shortcoming. It examines the origin and development of the depiction of the Attic helmet in Greek numismatics to highlight the significance of the noted developments.

Figure 1. Imitative Athenian coinage of Andragoras.

THE VOLUTE MOTIF

It is most notable that the closed circular loop, or volute termination of the pediment visor on Athena's helmet on the Series 2 coinage of Andragoras⁴ (Figure 1c-d) is not found on any other imitative Athenian coinage. This is a chronological indicator, that post-dates other imitative

³ Taylor (2019): the tetradrachms of Series 7 are separated from those of Series 2 by the Series 6 issues bearing the name of Andragoras. These latter display the head of Tyche on the obverse and a standing Athena armed for battle on the reverse. They are control linked by the *kerykeion* symbol to issues of Series 2, 7 and 8; refer Taylor (2020).

⁴ Taylor (2019): 53.

Athenian coinages, the production of which ceased early in the Hellenistic era.⁵ On other imitative Athenian coinage, the termination of the visor motif is defined by two parallel, or weakly convergent lines with either an open end (Figure 1b), or a sharp perpendicular truncation (Figure 1a) of the same form found on the Series 1 and the earliest of the Series 2 emissions of Andragoras. This is consistent with the depiction of the helmet on the Athenian prototype from the 5th to early 3rd centuries BC.

The floral ornamentation of Athena's helmet on Series 1 and 2 copies that of the Athenian Pi-style coinage dated to the second half of 4th and earliest years of the 3rd century BC (Figure 3a). However, the volute motif is absent from the portrayal of the helmet visor on the Athenian Pi-style coinage. Its first Athenian occurrence was on two 3rd century BC emissions; Heterogeneous Group B and C⁶ (Figure 3b), believed to be Athenian civic coinage⁷ dated to c. 270-260 BC (Group C) and c. 250-225 BC (Group B).⁸ By the 2nd century BC the volute motif was the norm on the Athenian coinage.

Heterogeneous Group C departed from prior Athenian issues not only in the introduction of the volute termination of the visor on the helmet, but also in the adjustment of the die axes towards 6 o'clock, struck with cylindrical dies.⁹ Identical changes are observed in the transition from the Andragoras Series 1 to Series 2 emissions, accompanied by the start of the depiction of the volute device on the visor on Athena's helmet.¹⁰ This is either a truly remarkable coincidence, or more plausibly the developments evident in the Athenian Heterogeneous Group C coinage were copied in the Series 2 imitative coinage struck in Parthia. Yet these developments in Series 2 marked the start of a divergence from the Athenian prototype. The Pi-style flora ornamentation of the helmet was retained in preference to the *Quadrigité* floral style of the Heterogeneous group. More significantly, the Athenian olive sprig and crescent on the upper left of the reverse was abandoned, displaced by multiple symbols (mint controls) unique to the mint. This was associated with a diversification in the coinage, including the introduction of iconographically differentiated small denominations including the Series 3 hemidrachms and drachms (Figure 2c) on which the Athenian owl was replaced by the Macedonian eagle on the reverse. From this it is evident that the introduction of the volute design motif, accompanying a new die adjustment and circular dies, marked a pivotal point in the coinage, one that ended what was previously a purely Athenian imitative influence.

⁵ Van Alfen (2011). For the reasons outlined in Taylor (2019) the politically neutral imitative Athenian coinage was revived for local needs in Parthia under the satrap Andragoras (Series 1 and 2). This was done in response to Seleukid monetary neglect of the province. Refer also to the Catalogue of New Varieties later in this volume for an example of a pseudo-Seleukid imitative owl struck somewhere in the east of the Seleukid realm in the first half of the 3rd century BC.

⁶ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): 14-16, pls.4-5.

⁷ Kroll (2013): 37-38.

⁸ Dating defined on the basis of their earliest occurrence of Athenian Heterogeneous Group C in the Krčedin 1953 Hoard (*CH* 9, 166) that closed c. 270-260 BC and the Phayttos 1918 Hoard (*IGCH* 159) that closed c. 260 BC. The dates of these hoards are subject to some uncertainty, but on the hoard data presented by Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990), it appears that Group C preceded Group B. Group C dates to the 2nd quarter of the 3rd century BC, while Group B is most likely of the third quarter of that century.

⁹ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): 20.

¹⁰ Taylor (2019): 53.

a. *Andragoras* Series 1.2 tetradrachm.
Helmet detail is based on the mid 4th century BC Athenian Pi-style (Pi II) type.
Roma Numismatics XVII, 588.

b. *Andragoras* Series 2.4 tetradrachm.
Introduction of the volute termination on the decorative visor, commencing with the didrachms of Series 2.2. It was established across all large denominations by 2.14.¹¹
Roma Numismatics XIX, 621.

c. *Andragoras* Series 3.7 drachm.
Drachms of the Athena/eagle Series 3 depict the volute termination from the outset.
Roma Numismatics XX, 328.

d. *Sophytes* Series 7.1 tetradrachm.
A metal helmet crest decorated with linked volutes, replaces the cropped horse hair depiction of the crest on preceding series.
Roma Numismatics XIV, 364.

e. *Sophytes* Series 8.2 tetradrachm.
Attic decorative elements on the helmet are replaced by a laurel wreath. Neck guard conforms to the nape of the neck to loop beneath the ear. A cheek guard is added to the helmet profile.
Roma Numismatics XV, 340.

Figure 2. Andragoras and Sophytes: progression in helmet depiction.

¹¹ Taylor (2019): 53.

Figure 3. Athenian tetradrachms: (a) Pi-style and (b) Heterogeneous Group B.

In summary, the volute termination of the pediment visor and the accompanying changes in coin fabric expressed in the Series 2 imitative owls of Parthia mirror the developments in the Athenian Heterogeneous Group C tetradrachms of the second quarter of the 3rd century BC. This serves to chronologically anchor the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage to around the middle of the 3rd century BC. This dispels the idea that it was struck in the 4th century BC, in some accounts even preceding the conquest of the Persian east by Alexander the Great.¹²

Origin of the Volute Motif on the Attic Helmet

The ornate Attic helmet depicted on the silver coinage of Athens, and its imitative counterparts, was an artistic conception originally based on the Chalcidian helmet type that originated among the Greek colonies of southern Italy in the 6th century BC,¹³ from which evolved the Attic military helmet by the 5th century BC.¹⁴ The style and detail of the helmet depicted on Athenian coinage evolved more slowly, incompletely conforming to the typology of the functional Attic military helmet. The key points of departure between the Athenian artistic conception and the Attic military helmet are the absence of a cheek guard and a visor of relatively reduced dimensions. This is best appreciated by reference to the typological definition of the Attic military helmet:

The helmet now known as the Attic type was also first developed in the later fifth century BC, but reached its zenith in the fourth. This group comprises a small and highly varied series of helmets from several distinct workshops. The paradigm of the Attic Type is a close-fitting helmet with a pediment over the low brow and an elongated visor, an integral crest attachment rising from the back of the helmet terminating abruptly in the front, hinged cheek pieces of anatomical form, and an integral neck guard closely conforming to the neck and leaving an opening for the ear.¹⁵

¹² Mitchiner (1975): 9; Nicolet-Pierre and Amandry (1990); Bopearachchi (1996); Bopearachchi(1998); Bordeaux and Bopearachchi (2018).

¹³ Snodgrass (1967): 69. Obert (2012): 49-50; Hixenbaugh (2019): 140-141.

¹⁴ Hixenbaugh (2019): 140-141, although some scholars consider the Attic helmet to be a sub-class of the Chalcidian type; Everson (2004):132.

¹⁵ Hixenbaugh (2019): 141-142.

In the corpus of surviving Attic military helmets,¹⁶ a closed circular loop terminating the pediment visor is found on one of the earliest examples from 5th century BC.¹⁷ This developed into a spiral volute in the 4th century BC,¹⁸ then to become a prominent, almost ubiquitous feature on Attic type military helmets from the 3rd century BC.¹⁹ Depictions in art appear to have followed a similar trajectory. In Attic red-figure vase art, the volute device on a helmet is found on some works dating from around the second half of the 5th century BC,²⁰ then to become the norm in the 3rd century BC. However, the iconography of the Athenian tetradrachm deferred to older artistic traditions in the portrayal of the Attic helmet with the result that the volute depiction did not emerge on the coinage until towards the middle of the 3rd century BC.²¹ This reflects conservatism in Athenian numismatic iconography which had an archaizing character throughout most of its history.

a. Lavva 78 a.
Volute terminated visor.
Cheek guard raised.
Nomos 4, 1283.

b. Lavva 144 h.
Volute terminated visor.
Cheek guard absent.
Triton XV, 645.

c. Lavva 163.
Volute terminated visor.
Cheek guard lowered.
Nomos 4, 1291.

d. Lavva 81d (this coin)
Reduced pediment visor.
No volute termination.
Cheek guard raised.
Nomos 4, 1284.

Figure 4. Thessaly, Pharsalos drachms: late 5th-early 4th century BC.

¹⁶ *Ibid*: 513-520.

¹⁷ *Ibid*: H91 bears a crude circular volute termination to the pediment visor.

¹⁸ *Ibid*: H93 exhibits a raised spiral volute.

¹⁹ *Ibid*: H94-H126.

²⁰ For example, the amphora with a young Athenian leaving for war: Martin von Wagner Museum Würzburg, Inventory No. HA 117.

²¹ Nicolet-Pierre and Kroll (1990): 14-16, pls.4-5, Athenian Heterogeneous Group B and C.

One of the earliest Greek numismatic depictions of the volute motif on Athena's Attic helmet occurred on some of the drachms of Pharsalos²² in Thessaly, struck in the late 5th-early 4th century BC (Figure 4). Unlike the Athenian depiction of the Attic helmet, these conform more closely to the typology of Attic military helmet including at times a hinged cheek guard, that was depicted in a raised (Figure 4a) or lowered (Figure 4c) position. Some examples omitted the cheek guard completely (Figure 4b). However, the volute termination was absent on a majority of this series (Figure 4d). These variations of detail in a single coin series are consistent with the early introduction of the volute motif into the iconographic repertoire, in advance of its almost universal adoption a century later. Similar developments are observed in the contemporary numismatic depictions found on various coinages of Magna Graecia. A century later similar depictions of the Attic helmet worn by Athena were widespread, particularly on the coinages of Asia Minor. Compared to the coinage of contemporary Greek states, Athens was a laggard in the adoption of an accurate numismatic depiction of the Attic military helmet. This is reflected in all imitative Athenian coinages, which remained true to the 5th-4th century BC Athenian prototypes, until the seminal Series 2 emission of Andragoras.

SOPHYTES' HELMET

In previous scholarship²³ chronological significance was attached to the superficially similar helmeted male head found on the obverse of Sopyhtes' coinage and that of the Susa victory coinage²⁴ of Seleukos I (Figure 5). This led to the inference that the obverse of the former arose from the latter, and therefore the two coinages were close contemporaries. However, a detailed comparison of the two obverse images reveals significant differences that argue against this. There are only two general components of shared imagery in the two depictions; the presence of a cheek guard and a volute terminated pediment visor on the helmet. Aside from the obvious differences in the adornment of the helmet, there are six significant differences of detail in the depictions that argue strongly against the inference that the Sophytes issue arose from a Susa precedent.

The helmet on the Sophytes issue has a metal crest decorated with a series of volute links (Figure 6). The helmet on the Susa issue is devoid of a crest. Significantly, the helmet on the Sophytes issues exposes the ear of the wearer, whereas that of the Susa type fully encloses the ear. In the course of the late 5th-4th century BC battle tactics evolved from a reliance on the brute force of a phalanx of heavily armoured foot soldiers to place greater emphasis on the mobility of a multiplicity of tactical units. Unimpeded hearing and sight became essential on the battlefield, particularly among the officer class. Lighter weight helmets with reduced facial guards and ear cut-outs delivered unimpeded vision and hearing. In this respect, the Sophytes issue depicts a technological advancement over that portrayed on the Susa coinage.

²² Lavva (2001); Fischer-Bossert (2003): 400-403. The chronology based on the die study of Lavva (2001) is doubtful, unconstrained by hoard analysis and most probably errs on the high side. An early to mid-4th century date is probable.

²³ Cunningham (1866): 222; Gardner (1886): xix-xx; Bopearachchi (1996): 25-26; Kritz (2017): 64-74; Jansari (2018): 74-76.

²⁴ Iossif (2004) and Marest-Caffey (2016) for a detailed examination of the Susa coinage, its polysemous imagery, die study and downdating to the early years of the 3rd century BC, following the Battle of Ipsos (301 BC).

a. Sophytes
Series 8.3 tetradrachm.
Roma Numismatics XIV, 365

b. Susa, Seleukos I
SC 173.16 tetradrachm.
Triton XXIII, 460

Figure 5. Tetradrachms: (a) Sophytes and (b) Susa (Seleukos I).

Detail: cheek guard tie

Figure 6. Enlargement of a Sophytes tetradrachm obverse (Series 8.3).

Roma Numismatics XIX, 624.

The detail of the cheek guard depicted on the Sophytes issue indicates that it is attached to the bowl of the helmet via a linear hinge along the base of the helmet bowl, whereas there is no visible mechanism of fixture of the cheek guard to the helmet bowl on the Susa depiction. It merges directly into the helmet bowl, apparently an integral component of a single piece helmet. Support for this interpretation of the Susa imagery is found in the detail. The cheek piece is not secured beneath the chin by a tie or strap, whereas on tetradrachms of Sophytes this detail is present in a fine strap that extends from the tip of the cheek piece to beneath the chin of the wearer with two strands of a knot visible (refer enlarged detail on Figure 6).

Another notable point of difference is the design of the neck guard of the helmet. That of the Sophytes helmet is smaller. It conforms very closely to the nape of the neck, looping down behind the exposed ear, consistent with the typology of the Attic military helmet. On the Susa depiction the neck guard is depicted as a heavier, more rigidly vertical component of the helmet. It does not conform closely to the nape of the neck and leaves no opening for the ear. The helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes is closer to a true-to-life depiction of an Attic military helmet, whereas that on the Susa issue of Seleukos I exhibits significant departures that more closely align it to an artistic conception dating to an earlier time.

Moving beyond the comparative details of the helmet to the totality of the depiction of the male head we find a notable departure in the base of the neck on the two types. That of the Sophytes emission is defined by a neck truncation on which a mint mark, MNA or M, can be discerned on two (Series 8.1 and 8.2) of the three issues. The MNA mint mark serves to link the Sophytes coinage to the last of the Series 1 and some of the earliest of the Series 2 imitative Athenian owls that also carry the MNA mint mark on the obverse, either immediately below, or behind the neck (Figure 2b).²⁵ In contrast, the base of the neck on the Susa type is concealed by a feline skin, tied at the front of the neck by the paws.

The six significant differences in detail between the two depictions of a helmeted male head far exceed the superficial general similarities. They suggest that the iconography of the helmeted male head on Sophytes coinage originated independently of the Susa type of Seleukos. More than a century ago the prominent British numismatist Barclay Head astutely noted that ‘the helmet of Sophytes on the obverse bears a very remarkable resemblance to the helmet of Athena on the drachms [Series 2] of the same Indian weight.’²⁶ Later Richard Whitehead perceptively stated that ‘The [Sophytes] drachm is not a direct imitation of any existing piece; the designs are original.’²⁷ Unfortunately, the incisive observations of these two scholars were ignored by subsequent generations in favour of a conjecture based on the very superficial resemblance to the Susa trophy issues of Seleukos I.

Archaeological support for the interpretation

The austere and functional helmet on the Sophytes coinage conforms to the typology of the Attic military helmet. In its depiction it is a further evolution of the Attic helmet worn by Athena on the Series 2 emission:

²⁵ Taylor (2019): 60 and table 2. Obverse mint marks in the form of Greek monograms or letters are an unusual characteristic of the coinage, one that sets it apart from its early Hellenistic contemporaries. The progression in the obverse mint marks is one of decreasing prominence, culminating in the placement of almost invisible mint marks on the neck truncation of two of the Sophytes issues.

²⁶ Head (1906): 14.

²⁷ Whitehead (1943): 60.

In the progression of iconographic detail from the Athena head of Series 2 to that of the androgynous Athena of Series 7 and then to the male head of Series 8 we see a series of details develop that argue more strongly for convergent evolution of the helmeted male head design, rather than a direct assimilation of the Susa types. The laurel wreath decoration of the helmet bowl, plus the bird wing adornment of the cheek guard, the latter thematically carrying through into the design an iconographic element associated with the dominant ‘birds of a feather’ iconography of the reverse of the coinage, argue strongly for a degree of convergent evolution of the helmeted head design, rather than assimilation. The helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes probably reflected reality. Supporting this idea, is a remarkable sculpted helmeted male head, dating to the second century BC, recovered in the excavations of the Parthian royal palace at Nisa, in eastern Parthia [Figure 7].²⁸ Although it bears a fulmen on the cheek guards, the helmet is of near identical form to that depicted on the Sophytes coins, including the detail of the metal crest. The sculpted head is inferred to be that of a Parthian soldier wearing a Hellenistic style helmet; the style of helmet influenced by the former enemy from whom control of Parthia was wrested.²⁹

Figure 7. Sculpted head of a 2nd century BC Parthian warrior from Nisa.

Just as depicted in fine detail on the tetradrachms of Sophytes (Figure 6), straps secure the cheek pieces beneath the chin on this Parthian sculpture (Figure 7). The published record of this sculpted head reads:

²⁸ Image source Reproduced from Wikimedia Commons; Farrokhi et al (2017): fig. 4 for a profile image of the Nisa helmeted head, which shows a volute element above the ear.

²⁹ Taylor (2019): 59-61.

This helmet, seen on the head of a Parthian soldier (broken off from its original clay sculpture), has a bowl shape with a high crest and a crenelated visor. With its Hellenic appearance, the Nisa helmet's inclusion of moveable cheek-pieces, suggest western (Greek) influence on Parthian military technology in the region at the time. This may be indicative of some type of contemporary Parthian military technological borrowings from the Seleucids (i.e. cheek-pieces).³⁰

Others disagree, suggesting that 'the Parthians never represented themselves as such' and that the sculpture of the helmeted head 'may have been part of a sculptural composition depicting Parthian victory over the Seleukids.'³¹ If so, it lends even more credence to the interpretation that the helmet depicted atop the male head of the Sophytes coinage is a true-to-life depiction of a Greco-Macedonian military helmet in use at the time of the conquest of Parthia by the Arsaces.

A similarly styled, heavily ornamented Attic military helmet of the period was found in a mid-3rd century BC warrior's burial at Kerch in the Crimea. Now housed in the Hermitage Museum collection³² it is believed to have originated from a workshop on Milos in the Cyclades in the first half of the 3rd century BC.³³ The overall design very closely approximates that of the Sophytes helmet. It bears an identical metal crest, volute terminated visor motif and cheek guards separated from the neck guard sufficiently to expose the ear of the wearer. On the right side of the helmet is preserved the outline of the linear hinge edge to which was affixed the cheek guard in an identical fashion to that depicted on the Sophytes coinage. The form of this 3rd century BC helmet could suffice as a model for the helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes.

Figure 8. Mural in the tomb of Lyson and Kallikles c. 250 BC.

³⁰ Farrokh et al (2017): 122.

³¹ Olbrycht (2017): 9.

³² The State Hermitage Museum of St. Petersburg (Inv. No. П.1834-42); Hixenbaugh (2019): fig. 72 and catalogue entry H109.

³³ Forged helmets manufactured in Greece were extensively exported to the eastern Mediterranean and Black sea regions in the 3rd century BC.

Supporting the 3rd century BC Greek origin of the portrayal of the helmet on the coinage of Sophytes, we find, within the scope of artistic licence, a somewhat similarly styled unadorned helmet on the left-hand side of a mural in the tomb of Macedonian aristocrat brothers Lyson and Kallikles, built c. 250 BC (Figure 8).³⁴ From this we can infer that helmets of the type depicted on the coinage of Sophytes were a component of the panoply of the officer class in the former Macedonian empire. Certainly, there is evidence in the archaeological record of 3rd century BC to argue that the Attic style helmet depicted on the coinage of Sophytes reflects one that was in use among the officers of various armies that campaigned in numerous theatres of war throughout the former Macedonian empire.

APOTHEOSIS

The combination of the decorative motifs on the Sophytes helmet is unique. The bird wing motif on the cheek guard thematically extends into the helmet a design motif associated with the ‘birds of a feather’ iconography of the reverse of the coinage (Series 1-5 and 7-8).³⁵ The linked volutes on the crest of the helmet continue the pattern established on the Series 7 tetradrachms (Figure 2d). This is an extension of the use of the volute motif first used to define the termination of the visor on the Series 2 coinage.

Figure 9. Stater of Perikle of Lycia c. 380-360 BC.

Roma Numismatics XVIII, 369 (enlarged \approx x2).

However, the placement of a laurel wreath on a helmet worn by a male head is without numismatic precedent.³⁶ In Greek art, the laureate helmet (Attic or Corinthian) was confined to depictions of Athena, while that of the laureate head was reserved for other deities, with one exception, that of Lycian dynast Perikle (Perikles in Greek), c. 380-360 BC. The latter via his laureate facing portrait sought to portray himself as a demigod on his silver staters (Figure 9). This was one of the earliest examples of a living mortal in numismatic portraiture, a development which occurred in a Persian, rather than a Greek cultural context.³⁷ Although ‘the dies were cut by local artists, they followed the contemporary conventions of Greek art in a marked departure from Achaemenid precedents.’³⁸

³⁴ Reproduced from Wikimedia Commons.

³⁵ Taylor (2019): 59-61.

³⁶ Pers. com. Rosanagh Mack (1 October, 2020) ‘Pre Romans, this [the laurel wreath] is only found on the head of divinities, the exception being the fourth century Lykian ruler, Perikles, but only on his bare head.’

³⁷ Sheedy (2011); Sheedy (2006).

³⁸ *Ibid.*: 122-23

This coincided with the Revolt of the Satraps (c. 370-360 BC) in Anatolia against the Great King, Artaxerxes II, in which Perikle declared himself king of Lycia. The revolt failed and the province of Lycia reverted to Persian rule. It was to be another century before the numismatic portraiture of a living mortal accompanied by an iconographic proclamation of divinity was accepted in Greek culture.

To this time, the laureate helmet was limited to depictions of Athena. It signified her role as the goddess of war in which capacity she could deliver military victory. Athena was the step-sister of the relatively unpopular³⁹ and capricious Ares, the god of war who was commonly portrayed wearing a helmet. In numismatic art the laurel wreath, or a laurel branch, was also used to symbolize divinely granted military victory. This usually occurred in an imagery of Nike bestowing the laurel wreath upon Zeus, Athena, a trophy, or in Hellenistic times the name of the king.⁴⁰ Therefore, the depiction of a laureate helmet worn by a male head on the coinage of Sophytes must carry military and divine symbolism. Two options are apparent. The laureate helmeted male head might be Ares, unusually for the time clean-shaven,⁴¹ or more plausibly, as argued below, the head is that of Sophytes assimilating some of the characteristics of Ares; a claim to divinity invoking the god of war. The difficulty in resolving this interpretive ambiguity is that Ares is infrequently depicted in Greek art, in which he is sometimes portrayed as a hoplite, readily mistaken as a mortal.⁴²

In the absence of a standard iconographic convention, or attribute unambiguously defining Ares, context is all-important when making an iconographic association with Ares.⁴³ On Sophytes' coinage, the consistently detailed portraiture of a clean-shaven male departs from the more usual contemporary Greek depictions of Ares. Although it cannot be completely discounted that the iconography depicts Ares, it would mark a significant departure from precedents in the Classical and early Hellenistic eras. The basis for an alternative interpretation lies in the historical context of the nascent independent state of Parthia and Sophytes. Sophytes briefly succeeded Andragoras in c. 240/39 BC.⁴⁴ The laurel wreath displayed on the helmet with its connotations of martial victory, was also associated with Athena, the primary deity appearing on the preceding coinage. As such, it would have been an appropriate symbolic motif to decorate the helmet of the commander of the military effort to stem the Parni invasion, albeit one that through its divine symbolism ran counter to Greek sensibilities of the Classical era. Such an application of the laurel wreath in numismatic iconography is unlikely to have occurred in the 4th century BC, at which time the iconographic

³⁹ Sparta was an exception to Ares general unpopularity in the Greek world. Unsurprisingly, in Sparta he was viewed as the model soldier and worshipped accordingly. The late 4th to 3rd century BC coinage of Phalanna in Thessaly frequently depicts a clean-shaven male head, either without helmet or helmeted, interpreted to be Ares. The non-laureate portrayal of the clean-shaven male heads, plus the ambiguity of the helmeted heads (are they male?) with the depiction of Athena makes for a doubtful identification of these Thessalian depictions as Ares.

⁴⁰ A possible iconographic association of Ares with the laurel wreath and branch is to be found on the 2nd century BC Iberian coinage of the *iliberris* which features a helmeted male head, Ares (?) before whom is what is usually described as a palm frond. Yet the latter bears a closer resemblance to the usual depiction of a laurel branch and on some examples what appear to be the buds of the laurel can be discerned.

⁴¹ A notable exception being the depiction of a youthful, clean shaven laureate Ares on some of the coinage of the mercenary Mamertinoi (Sons of Mars) from Messana, Sicily (288-278 BC). The clean-shaven Ares emerged in Greek numismatic art in the 3rd century BC becoming more frequent in the second century BC and later.

⁴² Mylonopoulos (2010): 196.

⁴³ Bruneau (1984): 487-489 notes the rarity with which Ares is identified on the basis of an inscription in Greek sculptural art. With his lack of defining attributes, it is the narrative context rather than Ares' individuality that defines his identity in an iconographic composition.

⁴⁴ Taylor (2019).

suggestion of apotheosis of a living individual was for the most part an anathema in Greek art and culture.⁴⁵ The latter even precluded numismatic portraiture of living people, which was considered an example of extreme hubris.

However, this cultural anathema did not prevent individual claims to divinity, which were met generally with scepticism and proved unpopular. Among the more high-profile Greek examples of the claims to divinity by a living mortal were the less than popular actions of Philip II of Macedon and his son Alexander the Great, who accorded themselves divine honours. The Orphic and Pythagorean concepts of divinity developed by the 5th century BC philosopher Empedokles of Akragas, who claimed to be divine, provided a philosophical framework for such individual claims.⁴⁶ Yet, with the exception of Alexander the Great, these individual claims to divinity did not manifest in iconographic representation. Arguably, the earliest Greek iconographic presentation of apotheosis occurred in a numismatic context with the Porus medallion, a decadrachm weight coinage depicting on the reverse an armoured male figure, inferred to be Alexander the Great, holding a thunderbolt in his extended right hand.⁴⁷ The thunderbolt was an iconographic attribute of Zeus and its application in the context of the iconography of the Porus medallion undoubtedly signified the divinity of Alexander the Great. Based on the hoard evidence, this remarkable item was struck toward the end of Alexander's lifetime, at the start of the last quarter of the 4th century BC.⁴⁸

The concept and iconographic depiction of apotheosis only gradually became a more broadly accepted practice among Alexander's successors and their descendants in the course of the 3rd century BC⁴⁹. With this increasing acceptance, Greek numismatic portraiture extended from that of deities on the obverse to that of mortal leaders, some of whom sought to present themselves with divine attributes.⁵⁰ This was followed in the 2nd century BC by epigraphic proclamations of mortal divinity on coinage.⁵¹ No longer restricted to kings, this even extended to magistrates on the coinage of Akarnanian Federation who it appears assimilated their image with that of Achelios, a proclamation of divine association, if not divine status.⁵²

⁴⁵ This didn't extend to the hero cult which posthumously conferred divine honours on an exceptional individual whose success was seen as evidence of divine potential.

⁴⁶ My thanks to Dr. Nicholas Molinari for bringing to my attention the example of Empedokles of Akragas and the reference to Wright (1995): 31 'in which souls (*daimons*) were once and could be again ὁ εὐδαιμονέστατος θεός (*ho eudaimonéstatos theós*). Essentially, souls like that of Empedokles were once gods but because of strife are now wandering daimons, but they can achieve this pure, divine state again, presumably while still living, since he was worshipped as a deity at Silenos after cleaning the river. This view was likely influenced by Pythagoras (cf. Porphyry, *Vita Pythagorae*, 19), who considered all souls as 'kin' and presumably part of a larger, cosmic nous. Pythagoras was also worshipped as a deity (Diogenes Laertius, *Vitae philosophorum*, 8.41).'

⁴⁷ Holt (2003): 42-46, pls. 2-5.

⁴⁸ Habicht et al (2018).

⁴⁹ Demetrios Poliorketes set the precedent commencing in 292 BC with the striking of coinage bearing his portrait displaying a prominent bull's horn protruding from his temple. Newell (1927): 72, pls. VII-XVI, 'the bul's horn, emblem of power and divinity and indicative of the divine power of kingship which he like his rivals, laid claim to appears above Demetrius' brow.' The reverse of this coinage is equally symbolic of Demetrius' divinity given the close association of the bull with the worship of Poseidon. *Ibid*: 73 'Thus we may recognize another bond, very clearly indicated between the king's portrait on the obverse and the fighting Poseidon of the reverse of our coins. The most important point of all, however, is the fact that Demetrius seems to have given himself out as the son of Poseidon. At least Athenaeus tells us that the Athenians actually hailed him son of Poseidon ...'

⁵⁰ For example, the horned head of Antiochos III (222-187 BC) depicted on some of his tetradrachm coinage.

⁵¹ For example, the legend on the tetradrachms of Antimachos I (c. 174-165 BC) of Baktria, ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΘΕΟΥ ANTIMAXΟΥ and that on the coinage of Antiochos IV (175-164 BC), ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ANTIOXΟΥ ΘΕΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ ΝΙΚΗΦΟΡΟΥ.

⁵² Molinari (2020).

In this evolving cultural and artistic milieu, the presence of the divinity-symbolizing laurel wreath on the helmet of a living mortal was a Greek numismatic first. As with Perikle of Lycia, this potential testing of the boundaries of Greek artistic and cultural norms occurred in a secessionist state, an overt rejection of the *status quo* that had failed the state of Parthia when confronted by nomadic invasion. The repeated failure of Seleukid kings to come to the aid of Parthia was the catalyst for secession by Andragoras. Appeals to a succession of Seleukid kings for assistance had apparently proved futile. Hence, the silver coinage issued in the name of Andragoras invoked Tyche, the tutelary defender goddess of cities, and Athena armed for war (Series 6). Conceivably, the failure of these invocations prompted the unusual invocation by Sophytes of Athena's capricious brother, Ares. With his predecessor slain by the Parni, an invocation to the god of war would have been the last recourse of Sophytes. This reflected the militarized nature of a nascent independent Parthia, a march state on the north-eastern frontier of Hellenic civilization.

The cockerel on the reverse of the Sophytes emissions (Figures 2d-e and 5a) lends credence to this interpretation. In Greek mythology Ares turned a youth, Alectryon (Ancient Greek: ἄλεκτρυών meaning rooster), once his beloved favourite, into a cockerel, forever to wake him at dawn, prepared for the possibility of an approaching enemy.⁵³ Just as the image of a deified Demetrios Poliorketes linked him to Poseidon on the reverse of his coinage, carrying the implication that he was son of Poseidon (refer Footnote 49), so we might infer that the association of the image of a deified Sophytes on the obverse, with a cockerel on the reverse, associates his proclaimed divinity with Ares. The appearance of the cockerel displacing the owl and eagle on the reverse of Andragoras' anepigraphic coinage is an abrupt punctuation in the iconography. It leads me to ponder the possibility that the abrupt turn around in the fortune and the demise of Andragoras was the result of a surprise attack of the Parni under Arsaces. Of this we'll never know. Yet such a possibility may have prompted his successor's invocation of Ares and the adoption of the cockerel motif on the coinage.

Notably the cockerel first appeared on the reverse of the Series 7 Sophytes issue accompanied by the helmeted head of Athena on the obverse. After one obverse die the helmeted head of Athena was replaced by that of Sophytes assimilating the characteristics of her brother Ares, the god of war (Series 8). The presentation of the image of Sophytes into an image invoking Ares might explain an unusual phenomenon observed on the Series 7 tetradrachms that bear the name of Sophytes. On these the head of Athena has distinctly masculine features,⁵⁴ most notably including a pronounced larynx (Adam's apple) that is comparable to the depiction on the succeeding Series 8 male head (Figure 2d-e). The profile and overall visage are close to identical to that of the male head presented on the Series 8 tetradrachms. The identification of Athena with what is at best described as an androgynous head on Series 7 is based solely on the decorative elements of the Attic helmet which are attributes of Athena. However, the male features, visage and profile of the head, suggest that it might equally well be interpreted as Sophytes assimilating the characteristics of Athena; perhaps an intermediate step to his subsequent depiction wearing a laureate Attic helmet.

Additionally, it has been remarked that in the outline of the cheek of the Series 7 Athena head there is a shape similar to the cheek guard of the helmet worn by Sophytes, the result of an

⁵³ Csapo (2006/07): 24, and sidenote 10 'Lucian *Gallus* 3. For the myth, see also the scholiast to Aristophanes *Av.* 835; Eustathius, *Ad Odysseam* 1.300; Ausonius, 26.2.27; Libanius, *Progymnasmata* 2.26.'

⁵⁴ Taylor (2019): 59.

originally engraved die with a cheek guard that was subsequently erased from the die prior to striking of the coinage.⁵⁵ However, it is more likely that the perceived outline of a cheek guard, if not an optical illusion,⁵⁶ was a preliminary outline on the die, a component of the engraving that was not taken to completion. If so, this could point to some hesitation in the initial step towards the depiction of Sophytes in the guise of a god.

These interpretive uncertainties aside, we can say with some confidence that the male features of Athena displayed on the Series 7 tetradrachms, accompanied by the depiction of the cockerel of Ares on the reverse marked an initial step towards the subsequent numismatic expression of Sophytes. On the subsequent issues of Sophytes the presence of the laurel wreath with its implication of divinity on Sophytes' helmet is inescapable. It can only signify Sophytes' claim to divinity, with the status of a demigod, one in which he sought to invoke the god of war, Ares the brother of Athena.

The gold staters of Andragoras

Supporting this interpretation is the previously unrecognized possibility that the god Ares might have been introduced in the iconography of the rare gold coinage of Sophytes predecessor, Andragoras. This possibility derives from an analysis of the iconography of his gold staters (Figure 10). The stater emission is known from a handful specimens struck from a single obverse die⁵⁷ and four reverse dies in three varieties distinguished by the presence or absence of dot/pellet/globule mint controls in the lower right field of the reverse.

Figure 10. Andragoras Av stater (no. 5)
(enlarged x4)

⁵⁵ Jansari (2018): 91.

⁵⁶ The vague appearance of an outline of a cheek guard on Series 7 may be an optical illusion, arising from the fact that the cheek guard on the coinage of Sophytes was of an anatomical form approximating that of the cheek itself.

⁵⁷ Based on images of varied quality, within the bounds of interpretative uncertainty the coinage appears to have been struck from a single obverse die that underwent episodes of recutting of the peripheral design elements in the detail of the hair and beard line on the neck and the leading hairs of front of the beard. This inferred retouching led Hill (1922) to the conclusion that two obverse dies were used in the coinage.

Obverse: Diademed and bearded male head r., Λ^P behind.

Reverse: ANΔΠΑΓΟΡΟΥ in exergue, male figure in panoply (Ares?) standing r. brandishing a spear in a chariot (quadriga) drawn r. by four horned horses driven by a winged goddess (Nike?) wielding a *kentron*.

Type 1. Rev. mint control: no dot mint control present.

	Obv.	Rev.	Grams	Die Axes	Provenance
1.	O1	R1	8.54	6	Numismatica Ars Classica AG 117 (2019), 223. Obverse die in earliest state of wear.
2.	O1	R2	8.45	n.r.	Münzkabinett Berlin 18202724. Very worn coin.

Type 2. Rev. mint control: three dots/pellets/globules in a triangular disposition to lower r. beneath the front legs of the horses.

3.	O1	R3	n.r.	n.r.	Private Coll.; Getty Images Europe 71508657MS014-MS015_quest; <i>The Quest for the Treasure of Mir-Zakah</i> .
4.	O1	R3	8.49	6	Numismatica Ars Classica 59 (2011), 652.
5.	O1	R3	8.50	6	Triton XX (2017), 341; NAC 78 (2014), 337; Triton XVI (2013), 550; purportedly from the second Mir Zakah Hoard.
6.	O1	R3	8.52	6	BM 1888,1208.59; Mitchiner (1975), Type 19.

Type 3. Rev. mint control: one dot/pellet/globule between the front and rear legs of the horses. A die flaw, or break defines a horizontal line above the dot so as to give the impression of a T shape.

7.	O1	R4	8.61	6	Roma Numismatics XXI, 307. Obverse die very worn, retouched on the beard.
8.	O1	R4	8.51	6	London, BM 1879,0401.2; Mørkholm (1991), pl. XXV, 378; Mitchiner (1975), Type 19; Whitehead (1943), pl. III, 5; Gardner (1879), pl.1,1. Obverse die extremely worn, retouched on the beard.

Previously doubt was expressed as to authenticity of this type of gold stater⁵⁸ and questions remain regarding the characteristics of some individual specimens.⁵⁹ However, in the context of an expanded corpus of the silver emissions of Andragoras and Sophytes the argument for the authenticity of this stater type is strengthened. The obverse mint mark Λ^P links the staters to the Andragoras tetradrachms, some of which also employ a reverse dot/globule/pellet mint control.⁶⁰ In turn these are linked by the same obverse mint mark to the preceding Series 2 imitative Athenian owls struck

⁵⁸ In the introduction to *BMC 28*, Hill stated 'I must confess that grave doubts may be entertained about the antiquity of many of these pieces' (Hill 1922, cxliv). Mørkholm (1991): 119-120 'The reconstruction of events is based on the assumption that the coins of Andragoras are genuine, and here I must confess to serious doubts, an attitude shared by a number of earlier scholars.'

⁵⁹ Triton XX Catalogue (2017): 114-115, lot 341 commentary. Suffice to note the concern, and that the existence fakes of the Andragoras stater does not undermine the fact that the type was an authentic issue.

⁶⁰ Taylor (2019): 41, Series 6.4.

under Andragoras prior to secession from the Seleukid realm, as well as the contemporaneous Series 3 Athena/Eagle drachms.⁶¹ Both gold and silver emissions were die adjusted with a 6 o'clock alignment, consistent with Series 2 and 3 issues to which they are mint control linked. The staters have a mean weight of 8.52 grams, consistent with the reduced Attic weight standard tetradrachms (c. 16.8 grams) of Andragoras.⁶²

Olbrycht⁶³ presented an analysis of the iconography of this coin type in which he identified the head on the obverse as that of Andragoras wearing the royal diadem, from which he concluded that the issue marked the secession of Parthia from the Seleukid realm and the elevation of Andragoras to the status of king. This would explain the presence of a solitary gold stater emission in an otherwise silver coinage system; a special emission marking a significant milestone for Andragoras and the newly created independent Parthian state.⁶⁴ However, the presentation of a bearded Andragoras on the obverse of the coinage presents a number of anomalies in the artistic context of the 3rd century BC. Depictions of bearded rulers at time this time are rare,⁶⁵ while the diadem is ambiguously depicted and could be seen as a tainia with its divine associations. The obverse image could just as readily be inferred to be that of the head of Zeus wearing a tainia.⁶⁶ This ambiguity in imagery is unlikely to have been accidental on a gold stater emission. Rather, it appears that the intention was to portray Andragoras with the characteristics of Zeus; a suggestion of the former's divinity and an invocation of the greatest god who we see unequivocally depicted with a laureate head on the contemporaneous Series 4 silver coinage of Andragoras.⁶⁷ If so, this provided a precedent for his successor's depiction with divine attributes.

Figure 11. Reverse detail (no. 7).

⁶¹ *Ibid*: Series 2.12, 2.14-2.16, 3.4 and 3.5, tables 2 and 3. Taylor (2020): tables 1 and 2.

⁶² *Ibid*: 66-75 for a metrological analysis of the silver coinage of Andragoras and Sophytes.

⁶³ Olbrycht (2020).

⁶⁴ Additionally, there exists a unique Sophytes gold stater entered commerce in 2005 documented by Bopearachchi and Flandrin (2005): 200-201. In all probability this coin is a modern fake. Refer Fischer-Bossert (2006) and Callataj (2013) for a rebuttal of Bopearachchi and Flandrin's proposed authenticity of the Sophytes stater.

⁶⁵ Olbrycht (2020): 197.

⁶⁶ Bellinger (1962).

⁶⁷ Taylor (2019).

Interpreting the reverse iconography Olbrycht noted that ‘The male figure in the quadriga is probably Andragoras: he has a long beard and wears a cuirass as well as a *kyrbasia* headdress with pointed top part. The winged figure may be identified as Nike.’⁶⁸ For the reasons outlined below, the winged figure certainly derives from Greek iconographic precedents defining Nike, although Olbrycht proffers an alternative identification of the winged figure as the Indo-Iranian goddess Anahita, the goddess of the waters, which he suggests symbolizes divine patronage for the ruler who he identifies as the male figure in the chariot.⁶⁹ However, the details of the head of the male figure in the chariot cannot be identified with confidence due to the poorly struck nature of this component of the imagery in the corpus of the coinage. On the clearest strikes, the male in the chariot is clean shaven, not bearded, negating the hypothesis that this figure is to be identified with the bearded head on the obverse, that of Andragoras. On the most complete examples of this component of the iconography (Figures 11 and 12) the male head appears to be wearing what is commonly termed a Phrygian helmet with cheek guards,⁷⁰ rather than a *kyrbasia* headdress. The Phrygian helmet with its pronounced forward leaning crest holder is of similar shape to the felt shepherd’s cap associated with Phrygia in Anatolia. Yet the helmet is found almost exclusively in ancient Thrace, reflecting its origin. More properly it is referred to as a Thracian helmet.⁷¹ It is very rarely depicted on Classical and early Hellenistic coinage. Notably however, it is the helmet worn by the male figure inferred to be deified Alexander the Great on the reverse of the Porus medallion. Moreover, Greeks believed that Ares, the god of war, dwelt in Thrace and it was with this region he was associated in the Homeric poems.⁷² The Thracian (Phrygian) helmet with its associations with the deified Alexander and the dwelling place of the god Ares, may be a pointer to the intended identity of the spear wielding male figure in the chariot. On some examples in the corpus we can identify the tip of a forward directed javelin, or spear, apparently held in the overhand hurling posture of the right arm of the chariot borne warrior (Figures 10 and 12), although no coin in the corpus displays a complete forearm and right hand due to consistently off centre strikes that leave this component of the iconography off-flan.⁷³ Based solely on the numismatic iconography, we can say definitely that the figure wears the cuirass and *pteryges* of a Greek warrior (Figures 10-12) and the overall depiction is that of a Greek warrior (god?) in a charging quadriga driven by a goddess (Nike ?), engaged in battle. To gain specific understanding of the identities of those in the chariot we must place this imagery in the context of the artistic conventions of the time, which in turn reflected Greek mythology and religious practices.

⁶⁸ Olbrycht (2020): 194.

⁶⁹ *Ibid*: 194-195.

⁷⁰ Hixenbaugh (2019): 141, types H29-H89.

⁷¹ *Ibid*: 141. Many Thracian also helmets bore anthropomorphic cheek guards that in shape and decoration mimicked a beard.

⁷² Millington (2013): 58, 190, 239, 247-249.

⁷³ It is notable that all coins in the sample exhibit a consistent off-flan strike of the upper left detail of the reverse. On no coin is this detail of the head and raised right arm of the male charioteer fully expressed. It appears that the reverse dies were cut oversize relative to most of the flans and that their placement in a hinged die holder with 6 o’clock adjustment led to a consistently off-centre reverse strike.

Figure 12. Downward directed spear held in overhand posture (no. 6).

Olbrycht struggled to place the reverse imagery in the art and numismatic repertoire of the time. He concluded that:

the motif of a horse quadriga is hardly attested among eastern Seleukid coin issues and remains a marginal phenomenon in the extremely rich repertoire of Seleukid coinages. Apparently Andragoras was inventive in his iconography and chose the motif deliberately, but he hardly had at his disposal any exact Seleukid prototype minted east of the Euphrates.⁷⁴

This assessment understates the difficulty of placing and interpreting the iconography in an appropriate art history context. No horse drawn quadriga is found on Seleukid precious metal coinage before the second quarter of the 2nd century BC, and only then on the gold staters of the usurper Timarchos (164-161 BC) that depict Nike in a horse drawn quadriga.⁷⁵ Some rare bronze issues of Seleukos II (246-242 BC) struck in Asia Minor similarly depict Nike in a horse drawn quadriga.⁷⁶ Figuring more prominently in Seleukid numismatic iconography is the quadriga bearing Athena drawn by four horned elephants. This is found on the coinage of Seleukos I struck across his mints in Babylonia, Susiana and Baktria in the first decade of the 3rd century BC.⁷⁷ In Hellenistic numismatics the horse drawn quadriga is almost invariably depicted carrying a deity, most frequently Nike, or more rarely Helios.⁷⁸ The prevalent association of the quadriga with the carriage of deities suggests that we must look beyond the interpretation that the armoured male in the chariot driven by Nike is Andragoras, a mere mortal.

From an interpretative standpoint a small, but most significant detail in the iconography of the reverse of the Andragoras staters has been overlooked in recent scholarship. The four horses drawing the chariot are horned. A curved horn protrudes from the forehead of each horse, extending back over the ear (Figure 11),⁷⁹ reminiscent of the horn of Ammon that figures prominently on the image of the deified Alexander on the coinage of Lysimachos. The depiction of a horned horse head emerged in the earliest Seleukid numismatic iconography. It signified the divine immortality

⁷⁴ Olbrycht (2020): 194.

⁷⁵ SC 1604.

⁷⁶ SC 738 and SC Ad28.

⁷⁷ Houghton and Lorber (2002): SC 130-132, SC 178 and SC 276-279.

⁷⁸ The former is exemplified by the gold staters of Kyrene during Ptolemy's satrapy c. 322-313 BC, while the coinage of Platon of Baktria c. 145-140 BC displays the more rarely encountered depiction of a quadriga borne Helios.

⁷⁹ Gardner (1879): 2-3 very astutely notes the detail of the horned horse heads on BM 1879,0401.2 struck from die R4 and its significance for the chronology of the coinage of Andragoras..

of a horse portrayed in such a manner.⁸⁰ The presence of a chariot drawn by four divine immortal horses most certainly indicates that the occupants of the chariot are deities. Significantly, in Greek mythology, Ares possessed four immortal horses, and in Greek art these are depicted drawing a chariot bearing Ares in battle. Moreover, in the Homeric Hymn to Ares (8), Nike is identified as the daughter of Ares, lending credence to the identification of the winged goddess driving the charging quadriga in battle.

Without doubt Andragoras was inventive, amply demonstrated by his approach to striking a politically neutral imitative Athenian coinage to meet local monetary needs while Parthia remained a neglected part of the Seleukid realm. On secession from the latter, his inventiveness extended to a new symbolic narrative based on Greek religion, literature and art, manifest in the coinage bearing his name, and in particular his gold staters. Ares the god of war was a chariot-rider in possession of four immortal horses (*Hippoi Areioi*); Aithion, Phlogios, Konabos and Phobos. These are portrayed in some examples of Attic red-figure art pulling a charging chariot bearing Ares hurling a spear. In Greek literature the Homeric Hymn 8 to Ares characterizes his attributes:⁸¹

Ares, exceeding in strength, chariot-rider, golden-helmed,
doughty in heart, shield-bearer, **saviour of cities**, harnessed in bronze,
strong of arm, unwearying, mighty with the spear, O defence of Olympus,
father of warlike Victory, ally of Themis,
stern governor of the rebellious, leader of righteous men,
sceptred King of manliness, who whirl your fiery sphere
among the planets in their sevenfold courses through the aether
wherein **your blazing steeds ever bear you above the third firmament of heaven;**
hear me, **helper of men, giver of dauntless youth!**
Shed down a kindly ray from above upon my life,
and strength of war, that I may be able to drive away
bitter cowardice from my head
and crush down the deceitful impulses of my soul.
Restrain also the keen fury of my heart which provokes me
to tread the ways of blood-curdling strife. Rather, O blessed one,
give you me boldness to abide within the harmless laws of peace,
avoiding strife and hatred and the violent fiends of death.

Components of the imagery contained in this hymn are found in a scene on the Milo Amphora housed in the Louvre.⁸² Dating to 400-390 BC it depicts the Battle of the Giants. One side of the amphora is dominated by the chariot of Ares driven by Aphrodite, accompanied by their son Eros, represented as an archer atop one of the four horses drawing the chariot. From the chariot Ares directs his spear in an overhand manner downward at the enemy. Another scene depicts a similar quadriga driven by Nike. The composition of the image of Ares engaged in battle from his quadriga is reminiscent

⁸⁰ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 7. Horns were used extensively in Seleukid numismatic iconography to signify the divinity of the horned entity, including on portraiture of the king.

⁸¹ *Homeric Hymns* 8, trans. Evelyn-White. Bold text denotes my emphasis of attributes evident in artistic depictions of Ares, and relevant to his invocation by Andragoras.

⁸² Musée du Louvre, Paris, Catalogue No. Louvre S1677.

of that on the reverse of the Andragoras stater. Certainly, the imagery of Ares directing a spear in an overhand manner from his chariot, drawn by his four immortal horses, was part of the Greek artistic oeuvre. In Greek literature Ares was also considered a saviour of cities. This complemented that of Tyche, the protector goddess of cities, depicted on the Series 6 tetradrachms of Andragoras to which the gold staters are linked by a shared mint control. Additionally, the appearance of Ares on the gold coinage of Andragoras might have been a numismatic allusion to the metaphor⁸³ applied to Ares in the chorus of Argive elders in Aeschylus' *Agamemnon* 437:

Ares, **gold-changer** of bodies
and balance-holder in spear-battle
from Ilium to loved ones
sends fired, heavy
dust, ill-wept, filling the handy urns
with ashes exchanged for men.⁸⁴

Metaphorically, in Greek mythology Ares was akin to a money-changer, or gold trader, assessing the value of lives lost in battle, determining the balance in the final outcome, as if a financial transaction.⁸⁵ In this sense the introduction of Ares onto the gold coinage of Andragoras might have been seen as a direct allusion to the metaphor contained in the mythological works underpinning Greek religious beliefs of the day. Certainly, it is not an interpretive stretch to suggest that the armed male figure in the quadriga is Ares, the god of war, accompanied by Nike, who in some mythology was his daughter, as well as the goddess of victory. This amounted to a numismatic invocation of Ares and Nike to deliver decisive victory in the ongoing conflict with the invading Parni. Seen in this light, the subsequent representation of Sophytes, the successor to Andragoras, as a demigod assimilating the some of the characteristics of Ares would have been a logical progression in this symbolic narrative.

An Indian Deity?

Recently it was conjectured that the helmeted male head on the Sophytes coinage portrayed a Hindu deity.⁸⁶ For a number of reasons it is unlikely that an Indian dynast in the Punjab, identified as Sopeithes of the ancient sources,⁸⁷ would have instigated this iconographic representation in the 4th century BC. The laurel wreath did not exist in Indian art or culture for the Bay tree (*Laurus nobilis*), the branches of which were used to construct the laurel wreath, was native only to the Mediterranean region. The concept of the rapid assimilation of Greek cultural and artistic influence

⁸³ My thanks to Dr. Nicholas Molinari for drawing this metaphor contained in the *Iliad* and *Agamemnon* to my attention: 'In the *Iliad* Ares is seen as a money changer presiding over the battlefield exchanging bodies like a financial transaction, and a similar theme runs in Aeschylus' *Agamemnon*.'

⁸⁴ Blakewell (2007): 123.

⁸⁵ *Ibid* for full discussion of this metaphor, which treats Ares role as analogous to that of the moneychanger who assesses the quality of gold, as does Ares assess men's value in battle.

⁸⁶ Jansari (2018): 76 suggested that the image may depict 'one of the deities that incorporated Indian and Iranian traditions and which were assimilated into the cult of Skanda,' a Hindu martial deity.

⁸⁷ *Ibid*, who following Cunningham (1886) equates the Sophytes with a local ruler Sopeithes (Arrian, *Anabasis* 6.2.2) in the Punjab.

and with it the symbolic divine association of the laurel wreath into the Indus Valley (the Punjab) in the tumultuous two decades following Alexander the Great's conquest is problematic. Early in this period Chandragupta Maurya (321-297 BC) took control of the entirety of the Indus Valley, removing this portion of the Macedonian empire from Greek control and influence. In 304 BC, in recognition of this geopolitical reality Seleukos formally ceded the Indus Valley (Punjab) and areas south of the Hindu Kush (Arachosia and Gedrosia) to the control of Chandragupta Maurya. Against this historical backdrop it is unlikely that a minor dynast in the last quarter of the 4th century BC, occupying a fiefdom in the Mauryan empire would adopt Greek artistic norms. More so when the latter include the divine association the laurel wreath to strike a novel coinage for local use. For similar reasons it is improbable that the coinage was the result of mintage by an otherwise unknown Indian general in Arachosia; a proposal founded in modern day identity politics based on the interpretation of a Greek language funerary epigram on a stele thought to date to the 1st century BC, purportedly found in the vicinity of Kandahar.⁸⁸

Tangible evidence that dispels the conjecture of an Indian origin for the coinage of Sophytes is present in the East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (*CH* 10.275) that was buried in c. 206-200 BC.⁸⁹ Found near Quetta in Pakistan in late 2001 the hoard consisted of 230 tetradrachms. It included a diverse range of material including lifetime Alexanders originating from as far away as Amphipolis, an array of posthumous Alexanders from Asia minor and various eastern mints, plus a few issues of Lysimachos and Attalos I, Seleucid issues down to Antiochos III (but excluding Seleucus III), five Baktrian issues from Diodotos II and Euthydemos I and most significantly a group of previously unknown imitative Alexander tetradrachms comprising about thirty percent of the hoard. Uniquely, in addition to the imitative Alexandrine coinage of local origin,⁹⁰ the hoard contained four previously unknown hybrid tetradrachms bearing an imitative Lysimachos obverse paired to an imitative Alexander reverse (Figure 13).⁹¹

Figure 13. Arachosia, Lysimachos/Alexander hybrid tetradrachm.
LWHT Coll. 285; *CH* 10.275, 181 (this coin).

The East Arachosia hoard offers an insight into the state of monetary circulation in Arachosia during the 125 years following the conquest of the region by Alexander the Great. It evidences the dominant presence of a contemporary Greek monetary influence in the region a century after

⁸⁸ Bernard et al (2004).

⁸⁹ Miller (2010); Van Alfen et al (2002): 183-186.

⁹⁰ An Arachosian origin for the imitative coinage is established by the presence of abundant die links in this component of the hoard's content. This is in addition to the fact that the types have not been found outside Arachosia.

⁹¹ Miller (2020): 106, catalogue nos. 180-183, pl. 16, 180-183; Van Alfen et al (2002): 183-186, nos. 460-462. Miller incorrectly refers to the presence of five hybrid type coins in the hoard, but his catalogue of the hoard's contents lists and illustrates only four hybrid type coins.

Seleukos formally ceded the province to Mauryan control.⁹² Absent from the hoard is the coinage of Sophytes. There is no evidence of Indian coinage circulating into the province, or being struck there in the late 4th and 3rd centuries BC. To the contrary, it appears that the province's coinage needs were met through a trickle of coinage from the distant west, accompanied by the striking of an imitative Alexandrine coinage. Based on the hoard record we can say with some confidence that on the eastern most frontier of the former Macedonian empire in Arachosia the models for the locally struck coinage were contemporary Greco-Macedonian types. The imitative Alexandrine tetradrachms and their hybrid associates were struck from crudely engraved dies lacking the finesse of the original coins which they sought to imitate. Nothing approaching the standard of engraving found on the imitative Athenian coinage of Andragoras, or that of Sophytes, has been found in the province.

Contrary to conjectures of an Indian origin for the coinage of Sophytes, the most straightforward and evidentially consistent explanation is that his distinctively Greek coinage originated further to the northwest in the fragmenting eastern Seleukid realm of the mid 3rd century BC, a region long neglected by a succession of Seleukid kings whose attention was diverted to the western provinces of the kingdom in a succession of dynastic conflicts.

CONCLUSIONS

The idea that the helmeted head on the Sophytes issue was based on that of the Seleukos I Susa victory coinage is misleading, one of several fallacies that have bedevilled attempts to formulate a coherent and historically consistent interpretation of the coinage. The differences between the two depictions far outweigh the few superficial points of similarity, to the extent that the argument that the former emulates the latter has no foundation. Rather, the depiction of Sophytes evolved separately, influenced by artistic developments in the imitative Athenian coinage that preceded it. With this insight, the dating of the coinage, including the preceding imitative Athenian owl and eagle emissions to the late 4th or earliest 3rd century BC⁹³ is unsustainable. A date no earlier than the mid 3rd century BC is consistent with the observed progression of the development of the coin fabric and iconography of the Series 2 imitative Athenian coinage that preceded that of Sophytes. The succeeding coinage bearing the names of Andragoras, then Sophytes, invoked Athena, Tyche, Ares and Nike in a symbolism that reads like a narrative in the context of the existential threat facing the secessionist march state of Parthia. This culminated in what appears to have been an unprecedented numismatic invocation of Ares on the coinage of Sophytes who sought to assimilate his image with that of the god of war in an ultimately unsuccessful attempt to counter the invading Parni, led by Arsaces.

⁹² *Ibid*: 107 'The local imitation Alexanders and Lysimachos hybrids indicate that the region continued to follow western coin types and design, rather than those to the north [Baktria], or the small silver bullion used to the east [India].'

⁹³ Nicolett-Pierre and Amandry (1990); Bopearachchi (1996) and (1998).

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